

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not always black in color. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear might be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 feet in length. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are a few of the most effective at climbing timber. Their relatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for protection, food, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their diet is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss program: Their diversified weight loss program gives them the power to reside in a large range of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the more than likely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per year. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and decreased habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the identify of the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals such as elk and moose. Their coloration varies from light blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft lengthy, and have a shoulder top of 3.3 ft. □□ Food plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than those found within the Rocky Mountains as a consequence of a richer diet. Annually there are forty six attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Recognized for their aggressive habits, grizzlies are responsible for the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Size: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight feet lengthy, and four feet tall on the shoulder. □□ Diet: Their eating regimen is similar to mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, as a consequence of extra plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social construction which results in less conflict between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is just one assault on humans every different year. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss program is usually made up of meat, often from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white but is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary within the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species attributable to lack of habitat from climate change. Despite their huge size polar bears will be quick, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slim head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Food plan: Their weight loss plan consists principally of animals, especially seals which they'll odor from a mile away. Although they appear white, their fur is definitely clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears could be extraordinarily harmful. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are rare due to the remote nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream [ikea panda teddy](#)

colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and sometimes widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account susceptible. □□ Measurement: One of many smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy

five inches tall. □□ Weight loss program: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on people are growing as folks encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently common in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its food regimen is bamboo. In truth, the second particular person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are thought-about a vulnerable species. □□ Size: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and can be over 4 ft tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at delivery. It additionally has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. □□ Eating regimen: In contrast to different bears the panda's eating regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo retains them common: they poop over forty instances a day! □□ Dangerous? Assaults are rare however dangerous, on condition that pandas have one in every of the very best chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is discovered within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its population is uncertain however thought-about weak and on the decline resulting from lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different physique parts utilized in traditional medicines. □□ Dimension: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising solar. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight loss program: Solar bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." Actually, they've an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Harmful? Because of its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they're thought-about susceptible. □□ Measurement: They are fifty five to seventy five inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to tell other than other Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very fast and can out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from bushes. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Food regimen: Their weight loss program consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They're one of the most aggressive bears, with essentially the most attacks on humans, mostly resulting from shock encounters. They blow the mud around with massive puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and don't mix nicely with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last brief-faced bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that look like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Size: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that generally seem like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. □□ Diet: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a weight loss program consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Dwelling in remote mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA exams were unable to determine what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas will not be bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in space. Most bear attacks occur

when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their very own household which might be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears.

1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that will point out a bear is nearby, through which case you want to be additional vigilant. Here are a number of tips you need to use to stop bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe.
2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are here so they don't by chance startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have great intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Secure YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** For those who see a bear, do not attempt to strategy or feed it. This consists of meals, but in addition your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, make sure that it is not less than 200 ft away from your tent so you don't entice bears to your campsite.
4. **Keep CALM.** If you happen to meet a bear, don't run. Attempt to make yourself look as big as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well prolong a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to grasp them up in a tree. Do not scream or attempt to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.
6. **Battle Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play lifeless. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 toes lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the biggest bear by both size and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight back with all your power and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is essentially the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for the most attacks. When in bear nation, it's always smart to carry bear spray. It's well deserved, particularly when cubs are around. Every year there are roughly 46 grizzly assaults, 6 resulting in dying. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome status. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per 12 months. When it comes to raw chunk energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and not to be messed with. When utilizing the chunk power quotient (bite power relative to size), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the hearth however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he turned an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-working public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless thru-hikers to attempt to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a accountability-free lifestyle. He also is perhaps the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada close to the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote The best way to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal parts backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to offer fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic suggestions, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

